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Approximate Taylor methods for ODEs

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Abstract

A new method for the numerical solution of ODEs is presented. This approach is based on an approximate formulation of the Taylor methods that has a much easier implementation than the original Taylor methods, since only the functions in the ODEs, and not their derivatives, are needed, just as in classical Runge-Kutta schemes. Compared to Runge-Kutta methods, the number of function evaluations to achieve a given order is higher, however with the present procedure it is much easier to produce arbitrary high-order schemes, which may be important in some applications. In many cases the new approach leads to an asymptotically lower computational cost when compared to the Taylor expansion based on exact derivatives. The numerical results that are obtained with our proposal are satisfactory and show that this approximate approach can attain results as good as the exact Taylor procedure with less implementation and computational effort.

Keywords: ODE integrators, Taylor methods, Faà di Bruno's formula

1. Introduction

In this paper we develop a numerical scheme consisting in an approximate formulation of Taylor methods for ODEs, akin to the scheme proposed by Zorío et. al. in [6] for hyperbolic conservation laws.

Taylor methods are based on differentiating the ODEs to obtain the high-order derivatives of the solution to be used in (truncated) Taylor series expansions for the next time step of the solution. The terms in the differentiation of a composition of functions may grow exponentially as the number of terms in the Taylor series does, thus leading to expressions that are difficult to obtain and costly to evaluate. The scheme proposed in this paper is much easier to

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implement due to its main strong point, which is that its implementation only depends on the functions in the ODEs and not on their high-order derivatives. Moreover, this scheme can be formulated to an arbitrary high order of accuracy with relative easiness and the computational cost increases quadratically as the order increases. Compared to relatively low-order Runge-Kutta methods, the number of function evaluations to achieve a given order is higher, however with the present procedure it is much easier to produce arbitrary high-order schemes, a feature that may be crucial for certain applications that require very high orders of accuracy and possibly extended precision arithmetic (see, e.g., [5, 1]).

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we review the Taylor methods for solving ODEs; in Section 3 we present the approximate Taylor methods and analyze their accuracy and stability; in Section 4 some numerical experiments are presented in order to show the performance of these schemes; finally, in Section 5 some conclusions are drawn.

2. Taylor methods

Without loss of generality, we consider initial value problems for systems of m autonomous ODEs for the unknown $u = u(t)$:

$$u' = f(u), u(0) = u_0, \quad (1)$$

for nonautonomous systems can be cast as autonomous systems by considering t as a new unknown and by correspondingly inserting a new equation $t' = 1$ and initial condition $t(0) = 0$.

We aim to obtain approximations $v_{h,n} \approx u(t_n)$ of the solution u of (1) on $t_n = nh$, $n = 0, \dots$, with spacing $h > 0$. We use the following notation for time derivatives of u (where we omit for simplicity the dependency on h):

$$u_n^{(l)} = \frac{d^l u(t_n)}{dt^l}.$$

Taylor methods aim to obtain an R -th order accurate numerical scheme, i.e., a scheme with a local truncation error of order $R+1$, using the Taylor expansion of the solution u from time t_n to the next time t_{n+1} :

$$u_{n+1}^{(0)} = u(t_{n+1}) = \sum_{l=0}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} u_n^{(l)} + \mathcal{O}(h^{R+1}).$$

Approximations $v_{h,n}^{(l)} \approx u_n^{(l)}$, $0 \leq l \leq R$, are substituted in the Taylor series, with $v_{h,n}^{(0)} = v_{h,n}$, $v_{h,n}^{(1)} = f(v_{h,n}^{(0)})$ and $v_{h,n}^{(l)}$, $2 \leq l \leq R$, computed by successive differentiation of $f(u)$ with respect to t . Truncation of the resulting series gives the R -th order Taylor method

$$v_{h,n+1} = v_{h,n+1}^{(0)} = \sum_{l=0}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} v_{h,n}^{(l)}.$$

As an example, the Taylor method for (1) in the scalar case ($m = 1$) for third order accuracy (see, for instance, [4] for more details) is computed as follows: the fact that u solves (1) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} u'' &= f(u)' = f'(u)u' \\ u''' &= f(u)'' = f''(u)(u')^2 + f'(u)u'', \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

which yields approximations

$$\begin{aligned} u'_n &\approx v_{h,n}^{(1)} = f(v_{h,n}^{(0)}) \\ u''_n &\approx v_{h,n}^{(2)} = f'(v_{h,n}^{(0)})v_{h,n}^{(1)} \\ u'''_n &\approx v_{h,n}^{(3)} = f''(v_{h,n}^{(0)})(v_{h,n}^{(1)})^2 + f'(v_{h,n}^{(0)})v_{h,n}^{(2)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

that result in the third order Taylor method

$$v_{h,n+1} = v_{h,n} + hv_{h,n}^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v_{h,n}^{(2)} + \frac{h^3}{6}v_{h,n}^{(3)}. \quad (4)$$

The following result [3], which is a generalization of the chain rule, describes a procedure to compute high-order derivatives of compositions of functions.

Theorem 1 (Faà di Bruno's formula). *Let $f : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $u : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ r times continuously differentiable. Then*

$$\frac{d^r f(u(t))}{dt^r} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{P}_r} \binom{r}{s} f^{(|s|)}(u(t)) D^s u(t), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_r = \{s \in \mathbb{N}^r / \sum_{j=1}^r js_j = r\}$, $|s| = \sum_{j=1}^r s_j$, $\binom{r}{s} = \frac{r!}{s_1! \dots s_r!}$, $D^s u(t)$ is an $m \times |s|$ matrix whose $(\sum_{l < j} s_l + i)$ -th column is given by

$$(D^s u(t))_{\sum_{l < j} s_l + i} = \frac{1}{j!} \frac{\partial^j u(x)}{\partial t^j}, \quad i = 1, \dots, s_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, r, \quad (6)$$

and the action of the k -th derivative tensor of f on a $m \times k$ matrix A is given by

$$f^{(k)}(u)A = \sum_{i_1, \dots, i_k=1}^m \frac{\partial^k f}{\partial u_{i_1} \dots \partial u_{i_k}}(u) A_{i_1,1} \dots A_{i_k,k}. \quad (7)$$

2.1. Computational cost

Faà di Bruno's formula can be used to obtain efficient implementations of Taylor methods if the derivatives $f^{(k)}(u)$ are available. These are typically obtained by symbolic calculations.

Specifically, the implementation of a Taylor method of order R requires $f_i^{(r)}(u)$, $i = 1, \dots, m$, for $r = 1, \dots, R - 1$. It is not easy to give a simple

expression for the number of terms in (5), but since $s_r = (r, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathcal{P}_r$, the terms

$$f_i^{(r)}(v_{h,n}) \overbrace{\left[v_{h,n}^{(1)} \quad \dots \quad v_{h,n}^{(1)} \right]}^r, \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (8)$$

corresponding to

$$f_i^{(|s_r|)}(u(t)) D^{s_r} u(t) = f_i^{(r)}(u(t)) \overbrace{[u'(t) \dots u'(t)]}^r$$

have to be computed. Assuming that no derivative of f_i vanishes and taking into account that the number of distinct r -th order derivatives is $\binom{m+r-1}{r}$, an efficient computation of (7), (8) would require about $(r-1)m^r$ products to account for $A_{i_1,1} \dots A_{i_r,r}$, m^r sums and $\binom{m+r-1}{r}$ computations of r -th order derivatives, $r \geq 0$, and corresponding products. Assuming a uniform computational cost for these r -th order derivatives of c_r operations, a fairly conservative lower bound for the computational cost for obtaining $v_{h,n}^{(r)}$, $r = 2, \dots, R$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & m \sum_{r=1}^{R-1} \left((r-1)m^r + m^r + \binom{m+r-1}{r} (c_r + 1) \right) \\ &= m \sum_{r=1}^{R-1} \left(rm^r + \binom{m+r-1}{r} (c_r + 1) \right). \end{aligned}$$

The computation of the first order term f_i is c_0 and the computation of the Taylor polynomial of order R for each component is $2R$, so the overall cost can be bounded from below by

$$C_T(R, m) = m \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} \left(rm^r + \binom{m+r-1}{r} (c_r + 1) \right). \quad (9)$$

For $m = 1$,

$$C_T(R, 1) \approx R^2 + \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} c_r. \quad (10)$$

For $m > 1$

$$C_T(R, m) \geq \tilde{C}_T(R, m) = (R-1)m^R + m \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} \binom{m+r-1}{r} (c_r + 1). \quad (11)$$

3. Approximate Taylor methods

We now present an alternative to the Taylor methods described in Section 2, which is much less expensive for large m, R and agnostic about the equation, in the sense that its only requirement is the knowledge of the function f defining the ODE. As proven below in Theorem 2, this technique is based on the fact that

the replacement of exact expressions of high-order derivatives of the function f that appear in Taylor methods, e.g., those in (2) for the third-order Taylor method, by approximations $v_{h,n}^{(l)} \approx u_n^{(l)}$, $l = 1, \dots, R$, such that

$$v_{h,n}^{(1)} = f(v_{h,n}^{(0)}), \quad v_{h,n}^{(l)} = u_n^{(l)} + \mathcal{O}(h^{R+1-l}), l = 2, \dots, R, \quad (12)$$

when $v_{h,n}^{(0)} = u(t_n)$, yields an $R - th$ order accurate scheme. In this work we compute the required approximations by simply using finite differences of sufficient order. Notice that the *exact* third order Taylor method, defined through (3) and (4), satisfies (12) with no error.

We introduce next some notation which will help in the description of the approximate method along this section.

For a function $u: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, we denote the function on the grid defined by a base point a and grid space h by

$$G_{a,h}(u): \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m, \quad G_{a,h}(u)_i = u(a + ih).$$

For naturals p, q , we denote by $\Delta_h^{p,q}$ the centered finite differences operator that approximates p -th order derivatives to order $2q$ on grids with spacing h , which, for any u sufficiently differentiable, satisfies (see [6, Proposition 1] for the details):

$$\Delta_h^{p,q} G_{a,h}(u) = u^{(p)}(a) + \mathcal{O}(h^{2q}). \quad (13)$$

We aim to define approximations $v_{h,n}^{(k)} \approx u_n^{(k)}$, $k = 0, \dots, R$, recursively. Given $v_{h,n}$, we start the recursion with

$$\begin{aligned} v_{h,n}^{(0)} &= v_{h,n}, \\ v_{h,n}^{(1)} &= f(v_{h,n}). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Associated to fixed h, n , once obtained $v_{h,n}^{(l)}$, $l = 0, \dots, k$ in the recursive process we define

$$v_{h,n}^{(k+1)} = \Delta_h^{k, \lceil \frac{R-k}{2} \rceil} \left(G_{0,h} \left(f(T_{h,n}^k) \right) \right), \quad (15)$$

where $T_{h,n}^k$ is the k -th degree approximate Taylor polynomial given by

$$T_{h,n}^k(\rho) = \sum_{l=0}^k \frac{v_{h,n}^{(l)}}{l!} \rho^l. \quad (16)$$

With this notation, the proposed scheme is:

$$v_{h,n+1} = v_{h,n} + \sum_{l=1}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} v_{h,n}^{(l)}. \quad (17)$$

The following result is a simplified adaptation of the corresponding result in [6].

Theorem 2. *The scheme defined by (15) and (17) is R -th order accurate.*

Proof. For the accuracy analysis of the local truncation error, we take

$$v_{h,n}^{(0)} = u(t_n), \quad (18)$$

and use induction on $k = 1, \dots, R$ to prove that

$$v_{h,n}^{(k)} = u_n^{(k)} + \mathcal{O}(h^{R-k+1}). \quad (19)$$

The result in (19) for $k = 1$ immediately follows, with no error, from the fact that u solves (1).

Assume now the result to hold for k and aim to prove it for $k+1 \leq R$. From (15) and (13), with $q = \lceil \frac{R-k}{2} \rceil$ and the notation $w = T_{h,n}^k$:

$$v_{h,n}^{(k+1)} = f(w)^{(k)}(0) + \mathcal{O}(h^{2q}). \quad (20)$$

Faà di Bruno's formula (5) applied to $f(w)$ and $f(u)$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} f(w)^{(k)}(0) &= \sum_{s \in \mathcal{P}_k} \binom{k}{s} f^{(|s|)}(w(0)) (D^s w(0)), \\ D^s w(0) &= \left[\overbrace{\frac{w^{(1)}(0)}{1!} \cdots \frac{w^{(1)}(0)}{1!}}^{s_1} \cdots \overbrace{\frac{w^{(k)}(0)}{k!} \cdots \frac{w^{(k)}(0)}{k!}}^{s_k} \right], \\ D^s w(0) &= \left[\overbrace{\frac{w_{h,n}^{(1)}}{1!} \cdots \frac{v_{h,n}^{(1)}}{1!}}^{s_1} \cdots \overbrace{\frac{v_{h,n}^{(k)}}{k!} \cdots \frac{v_{h,n}^{(k)}}{k!}}^{s_k} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u)^{(k)}(t_n) &= \sum_{s \in \mathcal{P}_k} \binom{k}{s} f^{(|s|)}(u(t_n)) (D^s u(t_n)), \\ D^s u(t_n) &= \left[\overbrace{\frac{u^{(1)}(t_n)}{1!} \cdots \frac{u^{(1)}(t_n)}{1!}}^{s_1} \cdots \overbrace{\frac{u^{(k)}(t_n)}{k!} \cdots \frac{u^{(k)}(t_n)}{k!}}^{s_k} \right], \\ D^s u(t_n) &= \left[\overbrace{\frac{u_n^{(1)}}{1!} \cdots \frac{u_n^{(1)}}{1!}}^{s_1} \cdots \overbrace{\frac{u_n^{(k)}}{k!} \cdots \frac{u_n^{(k)}}{k!}}^{s_k} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

We have $w(0) = v_{h,n}^{(0)} = u(t_n)$ and, by induction, i.e., (19), we have:

$$v_{h,n}^{(l)} = u_n^{(l)} + \mathcal{O}(h^{R-l+1}), \quad l = 1, \dots, k. \quad (23)$$

For any $s \in \mathcal{P}_k$, $D^s w(0)$ is a $m \times |s|$ matrix, and for any $\mu \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $\nu \in \{1, \dots, |s|\}$, we have from (6), (21), (22) and (23) that

$$(D^s w(0) - D^s u(t_n))_{\mu, \nu} = \frac{(v_{h,n}^{(l)} - u_n^{(l)})_{\mu}}{l!} = \mathcal{O}(h^{R-l+1}), \quad l = l(s, \nu) \leq k. \quad (24)$$

We deduce from (24), (7), (21), (22) that

$$f(w)^{(k)}(0) - f(u)^{(k)}(t_n) = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{P}_k} \binom{k}{s} f^{(|s|)}(u(t_n))(D^s w(0) - D^s u(t_n)) = \mathcal{O}(h^{R-k+1}). \quad (25)$$

Now, since $2q \leq R - k$, (20), (22) and (25) yield:

$$v_{h,n}^{(k+1)} - u_n^{(k+1)} = \mathcal{O}(h^{R-k+1}) + \mathcal{O}(h^{2q}) = \mathcal{O}(h^{R-k}),$$

which concludes the proof of (19).

The local truncation error is given by

$$E_L(t_n, h) = u_{n+1}^{(0)} - \sum_{l=0}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} v_{h,n}^{(l)},$$

where $v_{h,n}^{(l)}$ are computed from $v_{h,n}^{(0)} = u(t_n)$. Taylor expansion of the first term and the estimates in (19) yield that

$$\begin{aligned} E_L(t_n, h) &= \sum_{l=1}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} (u_n^{(l)} - v_{h,n}^{(l)}) + \mathcal{O}(h^{R+1}) \\ &= \sum_{l=1}^R \frac{h^l}{l!} \mathcal{O}(h^{R-l+1}) + \mathcal{O}(h^{R+1}) = \mathcal{O}(h^{R+1}). \end{aligned}$$

□

3.1. Computational cost

From (15) and the centered finite difference formulas obtained in [6, Proposition 1] we may deduce that the computation of $v_{h,n}^{(l)}$, for $l = 1, \dots, k$ requires about R^2 evaluations of f , and $4mR^2$ floating point operations. The $2mR$ floating point operations for the evaluation of the polynomial in (17) are neglected in this computation, for having a lower order in R than the previous terms. With the notation of section 2.1, the approximate computational cost is

$$C_{AT} = mR^2(c_0 + 4). \quad (26)$$

A comparison of this expression with (10) and (11) leads to the conclusion that our proposal should have a much smaller computational cost for large m for tightly coupled systems, for which very few or none of the derivatives of the ODE vanish. On the contrary, for $m = 1$, the advantage is not clear and it will depend on the ratios c_r/c_0 , $r = 1, \dots, R - 1$.

We consider, for instance, the application of this for the system of rational equations

$$\begin{aligned} u'_i &= f_i(u_1, \dots, u_m) = \frac{p_i(u_1, \dots, u_m)}{q_i(u_1, \dots, u_m)}, \\ p_i(u_1, \dots, u_m) &= \sum_j \alpha_{i,j} u_j, \quad q_i(u_1, \dots, u_m) = \sum_j \beta_{i,j} u_j. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

It can be seen by using the general Leibniz rule that computing an r -th order partial derivative, for $r \geq 2$, from already computed lower order derivatives needs $2r$ operations ($r - 1$ sums, r products by the coefficients β and one extra product by the inverse of the denominators), so that one can take $c_r = 2r$ in (11), for $r \geq 2$. First-order derivatives can be computed with $c_1 = 3$ operations and function values $f_i(u_1, \dots, u_m)$ take about $4m$ operations, so that $c_0 = 4m$. With this numbers, the quotient of (11) and (26) is

$$\begin{aligned} Q(m, R) &= \frac{\tilde{C}_T(R, m)}{C_{AT}(R, m)} = \frac{(R-1)m^R + m \sum_{r=0}^{R-1} \binom{m+r-1}{r} (c_r + 1)}{mR^2(c_0 + 4)} \\ &\geq \frac{(R-1)m^{R-1} + 4m + 4(m+1) + \sum_{r=2}^{R-1} \binom{m+r-1}{r} (2r+1)}{4(m+1)R^2} \\ &\geq \frac{(R-1)m^{R-1} + 8m + \sum_{r=2}^{R-1} \binom{m+r-1}{r} (2r+1)}{4(m+1)R^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Since, for $R > 3$, $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} Q(m, R) = \infty$ and, for $m > 1$, $\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} Q(m, R) = \infty$, the computational savings for our proposal are asymptotically guaranteed in a case like the present one, in which the unknowns are strongly coupled.

3.2. Low order approximate Taylor methods

For notational simplicity, we drop the subindex h, n from $v_{h,n}^{(l)}$. Following the procedure in (15)–(17), we have

$$v^{(1)} = f(v).$$

We compute approximations of the second order time derivative of u , $u^{(2)}$, by performing the following operation:

$$v^{(2)} = \frac{f(v + hv^{(1)}) - f(v - hv^{(1)})}{2h}. \quad (29)$$

Therefore, the second order approximate Taylor method reads as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{n+1} &= v + hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)} \\ &= v + h \left(f(v) + \frac{1}{4}f(v + hv^{(1)}) - \frac{1}{4}f(v - hv^{(1)}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that this method can be regarded as a Runge-Kutta method with 3 stages and the following Butcher array:

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \hline & 1 & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} \end{array}.$$

It is also worth pointing out that the application of this method to the equation $u' = \lambda u$ results in the time-stepping

$$v_{n+1} = (1 + h\lambda + \frac{1}{2}(h\lambda)^2)v_n,$$

and therefore the second order approximate Taylor method has the same absolute stability region as its exact counterpart.

The approximation of $u^{(3)}$ is obtained in a similar fashion:

$$v^{(3)} = \frac{f(v + hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)}) - 2f(v) + f(v - hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)})}{h^2}. \quad (30)$$

The next time step is then computed through the third order Taylor expansion replacing the derivatives with their corresponding approximations in (29) and (30):

$$\begin{aligned} v_{n+1} &= v + hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)} + \frac{h^3}{6}v^{(3)} \\ &= v + h\left(f(v) + \frac{1}{4}(f(v + hv^{(1)}) - f(v - hv^{(1)}))\right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6}\left(f(v + hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)}) - 2f(v) + f(v - hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)})\right) \\ &= v + h\left(\frac{2}{3}f(v) + \frac{1}{4}f(v + hv^{(1)}) - \frac{1}{4}f(v - hv^{(1)})\right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6}f\left(v + hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)}\right) + \frac{1}{6}f\left(v - hv^{(1)} + \frac{h^2}{2}v^{(2)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

It can be readily seen that the third-order approximate Taylor method is a 5-stages Runge-Kutta method with Butcher array given by:

$$\begin{array}{c|ccccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & 0 & 0 \\ \hline & \frac{2}{3} & -\frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{6} & \frac{1}{6} \end{array}$$

We conjecture that the R -th order approximate Taylor method can be cast as a Runge-Kutta method with $R^2 + \mathcal{O}(R)$ stages, which is larger than the upper bound on the number of stages to achieve R -th order given in [2, Theorem 324C, page 188]: $\frac{3}{8}R^2 + \mathcal{O}(R)$.

4. Numerical experiments

We analyze the exact and approximate Taylor methods with several numerical examples. We compare the order of the numerical error and the performance

of both algorithms. For these experiments, in the cases where the exact solution is unknown, we take as reference solution the one computed with the same method with a mesh refined by a factor of 10 with respect to the finer discretization considered in the experiment. Regarding performance, the times indicated correspond to the average of multiple runs. The exact Taylor method was computed with the help of MATLAB's symbolic toolbox. The `simplify` command was used on each term of the Taylor expansion.

4.1. Scalar equations

We consider in this subsection three problems with different complexity to analyze the method. As a first example we consider the problem

$$\begin{cases} u' = \sin(u), \\ u(t_0) = u_0. \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

whose exact solution is given by

$$u(t) = \cot^{-1} \left(e^{t_0-t} \cot \left(\frac{u_0}{2} \right) \right).$$

The results for $t_0 = 0, u_0 = \frac{\pi}{2}, T = 1$ can be seen in Figure 1.

The second example is given by a Ricatti equation:

$$\begin{cases} u' = -2tu + u^2 + t^2 + 1, \\ u(t_0) = u_0, \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

with exact solution

$$u(t) = \frac{1}{C-t} + t, \quad C = \frac{1 + (u_0 - t_0)t_0}{u_0 - t_0}, \quad u_0 < t_0.$$

The results for this problem corresponding to $t_0 = 2, u_0 = 1, T = 10$ are shown in Figure 2.

The last scalar example corresponds to an equation involving a logarithm:

$$\begin{cases} u' = \frac{u}{t} \log \left(\frac{u}{t} \right), \\ u(t_0) = u_0. \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

The exact solution of (33) is given by

$$u(t) = te^{Ct+1}, \quad C = \frac{\log \left(\frac{u_0}{t_0} \right) - 1}{t_0}, \quad t_0 > 0, u_0 > 0.$$

Figure 3 shows the results obtained for the case $t_0 = 1, u_0 = 1, T = 8$.

From these experiments we observe that for both problems (31) and (32) the approximate method outperforms the exact one for low orders, being the latter more competitive as the order increases. This is probably due to the fact that the terms that appear in the Taylor expansion of u involve many repeated trigonometric functions that are evaluated at the same point, thus taking advantage of simplifications in the expressions. In contrast, in the third

Figure 1: Problem (31). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 2: Problem (32). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 3: Problem (33). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$.

example, corresponding to problem (33) the approximate method obtains a sustained higher performance, as the Taylor terms in this case involve rational functions that contain a large number of factors and do not simplify as easily as in the other examples. We also observe in the right plots corresponding to the third example a discrepancy in the absolute errors obtained by both methods that was barely observable in the previous examples.

4.2. Systems of ODE

We consider two problems modeled by systems of ODE. The first example models a pendulum suspended on an elastic spring or cord. Its position $(r_1(t), r_2(t))$ and velocity $(v_1(t), v_2(t))$ can be modeled with the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1' &= v_1, \\ r_2' &= v_2, \\ v_1' &= k_1 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2}} - 1 \right) r_1 - k_2 v_1, \\ v_2' &= k_1 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{r_1^2 + r_2^2}} - 1 \right) r_2 - k_2 v_2 - g, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where k_1 defines the elasticity of the cord, k_2 is related to the friction of the pendulum and g is the gravitational acceleration. The initial conditions considered in this experiment are $r_1(0) = 0.7$ m, $r_2(0) = -0.8$ m, $v_1(0) = 0.1$ m/s, and $v_2(0) = -0.6$ m/s, for time $T = 10$ s and the parameters are taken as $m = 1$ Kg, $g = 9.81$ m/s², $k_1 = 100$ N/m, $k_2 = 1$ Kg/s. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Our next example corresponds to a biological model related to gene regulation, known as *toggle switch*. The toggle switch models the interaction of two genes, indexed L and R that repress mutually:

$$\begin{aligned} m_L' &= k_{L,1} \frac{K_R^{n_R}}{K_R^{n_R} + p_R^{n_R}} - d_{L,1} m_L, \\ p_L' &= k_{L,2} m_L - d_{L,2} p_L, \\ m_R' &= k_{R,1} \frac{K_L^{n_L}}{K_L^{n_L} + p_L^{n_L}} - d_{R,1} m_R, \\ p_R' &= k_{R,2} m_R - d_{R,2} p_R. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Quantities $m_{\{L,R\}}$ represent the concentration for gene $\{L, R\}$ Messenger Ribonucleic Acid (mRNA) and $p_{\{L,R\}}$ the concentration of gene $\{L, R\}$ protein. The parameters are all set to 1 except $n_L = n_R = 2$, $k_{L,1} = k_{R,1} = 10$, with initial conditions $m_L(0) = 0.5$, $p_L(0) = 0.4$, $m_R(0) = 0.5$, $p_R(0) = 0.3$, for $T = 10$. Results for this problem can be seen in Figure 5.

We consider also systems of ODE defined through homogeneous rational functions as used in Section 3.1 to analyze the computational complexity of exact Taylor methods. Figure 6 shows the results corresponding to the solution of (27) for the case $m = 6$ for orders 2, 4, and 6, for time $T = 10$ and initial conditions $u_i(0) = 1$, $i = 1, \dots, m$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

Figure 4: Problem (34). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$; (g)-(h) $R = 8$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

Figure 5: Problem (35). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$; (g)-(h) $R = 8$.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 6: Problem (27). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . (a)-(b) $R = 2$; (c)-(d) $R = 4$; (e)-(f) $R = 6$.

R	m			
	4	5	6	7
2	0.2288	0.2564	0.3026	0.4157
4	1.0531	2.5117	5.6411	14.9425
6	8.4649	28.6859	58.5005	110.6603

Table 1: Ratio of CPU time between the computational costs of exact and approximate R -th order Taylor methods for the rational system (27).

Figure 7: Problem (27). Left: Error vs CPU time, Right: Error vs. h . $R = 4$, rational function $m = 4$.

In the case of systems we observe an increasing performance of the approximate version with respect to the exact version as the order increases.

In the last test we consider the comparison of the numerical solution of (27) with the classical fourth-order Runge-Kutta method and the fourth-order approximate Taylor method. We consider the case $m = 4$ for time $T = 10$ and initial conditions $u_i(0) = 1$, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Global errors are approximated from a reference solution computed by the fourth order Runge-Kutta method for $n = 1000000$ time steps.

In Figure 7 we display the results of this comparison. The expected conclusion is that the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method is more efficient than the corresponding approximate Taylor method and that both have fourth order global errors.

5. Conclusions

We have proposed a technique to obtain ODE integrators of arbitrary order that can be regarded as approximate Taylor methods. The clear advantage of our proposal with respect to exact Taylor methods is that only function

evaluations are needed, so the cost of implementation is very low. We have performed some numerical experiments that show that approximate Taylor methods achieve the design order of accuracy, both methods have roughly the same accuracy and that approximate methods can be more computationally efficient in some cases, specially for moderate or large tightly coupled ODE systems. As future research along the subject of approximate Taylor methods, we consider the study of their relationship with Runge-Kutta methods and their stability.

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